

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

It gives me great pleasure to announce the ninth regular issue of 2022. I would like to thank all the authors for their sound research and the editorial board for their extremely valuable reviews and suggestions for improvement. These contributions, together with the generous support of the consortium members and the recognition from the research community, enable us to run our journal and maintain its quality.

Still, I would like to expand our editorial board: If you are a tenured associate professor or above with a good publication record, please apply to join our editorial board. We are also interested in receiving high-quality proposals for special issues on new topics and emerging trends.

In this regular issue, I am very pleased to introduce four accepted papers from 18 authors from six different countries.

In a research collaboration between Ecuador, Spain and Argentina, Alexandra Corral, Luis E. Sanchez and Leandro Antonelli focus on improving the software development process to overcome the lack of communication regarding an understanding of the discourse domain and to integrate and process excessive information from different sources using intelligent systems and semantic reasoning. Fatemeh Farnaghi-Zadeh, Mohsen Rahmani and Maryam Amiri from Iran propose an improved approach to feature selection based on target Points To compute neighborhood relations (EPSTEIN). Zohra Mehenaoui, Yacine Lafifi and Layachi Zemmouri from Algeria present an automatic approach to identifying learning styles based on patterns of learning behavior with respect to the Felder and Silverman Learning Style Model (FSLSM) and report about their study of 73 students enrolled in online courses. Last but not least, in a collaboration between Spain and Italy, Aurora Polo-Rodríguez, Pietro Dionisio, Francesco Agnoloni, Ana Perandrés Gómez, Cristiano Paggetti, Lucía González López, Alfonso Cruz Lendínez, Macarena Espinilla- Estévez and Javier Medina-Quero present their research on ubiquitous and wearable solutions to address active ageing and report about a pilot project implemented for the Andalusian community.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

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